

Design and fabrication of novel MIL-53(Fe)/MIL-101(Cr)/NiFe₂O₄ nanocomposite towards sonocatalytic degradation of toxic organic dyes

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Abstract

In this research, the sonocatalytic performance of the novel magnetically separable MIL-53(Fe)/MIL-101(Cr)/NiFe₂O₄ nanocomposite was investigated by the H₂O₂-assisted ultrasonic system for the degradation of water soluble organic dye contaminants, involving methylene blue (MB), rhodamine B (RhB) and methyl orange (MO). The MIL-53(Fe)/MIL-101(Cr)/NiFe₂O₄ nanocomposite was synthesized via the ultrasonic-assisted hydrothermal method. The FESEM/EDAX, XRD, FTIR, VSM, and BET were applied for the identification of the morphology and structure of the as-manufactured nanocomposite. Compared with H₂O₂/sonolysis, the higher degradation of MB dye (25 mg/L) was attained by the sonocatalytic reaction. Plus, by the addition of hydroxyl radical (•OH) and hole quenchers decreased the degradation yield from 97% to 32% and 74% after 20 min, indicating the •OH free radicals as main oxidizing agent of the above-mentioned process. As well, the magnetic feature of the sample helped for quickly separation of the nanocomposite, made it recyclable with a trivial decline in the activity even after 4 sequential cycles.

Keywords: MIL-53(Fe)/MIL-101(Cr)/NiFe₂O₄, metal organic framework, nanocomposite, catalyst, organic dyes, sonodegradation.